

Supplementary Information 10 – Shell growth model

The growth of the shells of *C. symbolicum* and *C. giganteum* was studied based on a combination of micro- and macroscopic observations (**Fig S1**). The growth of the shell was inferred from the identification of shell growth increments on high resolution color scans of cross sections through the shells and microscopic observations and counting of regular growth increments in the shell aragonite using cross polarized and plain polarized light microscopy (**S16-18**), combined with the analyses of growth in other gastropod species from the literature (Tojo and Ohno, 1999). Microscopic increments could be traced around the whorls in cross section through the shells of *Campanile giganteum* and were used as basis for the reconstruction of complex, three dimensional growth patterns in the shell, which in term served as bases for the alignment of chemical measurements in the columella and on the outside of the shell to a common chronology. The chronology of the shells in cross section shows that extension of the gastropod shell happens by adding aragonite to the aperture, causing the aperture to extend away from the apex in clockwise helicoidal direction as seen from the apex of the shell. After laying the foundations of a new part of the shell, mineralization of aragonite on the inside of the helix thickens the walls.

Fig S1: Showing the direction of growth in a cross section through the shell of *Campanile symbolicum*. Darker colored segments were deposited early while increasingly lighter segments were deposited at a later stage.

In order to keep track of the sampling along the helix on the outside of the shell, a reference line was constructed that ran longitudinally from the apex to the aperture along the outside of the shell. This line was defined as the starting point for each rotation of the shell along the helix, with later sections of the shell deposited away from the line downward in clockwise direction (as seen from the apex). Arbitrary construction of this reference line was necessary because the shell whorl spirals continuously around the columella in helicoidal direction, making the shell roughly symmetrical in shape relative to the columella, with no physical distinction between different parts along the helix. Positions of samples drilled on the outside of the shell were determined by giving the “level” of the whorl (i.e. the number of whorls that could be counted above the whorl that contains the sample; L) and the position on this level relative to the reference line (P ; with 0 being on the reference line and 0.999... being very close to the reference line where the whorl below starts; see **Fig S2**). This way, every sample obtained a value (W) that represented its distance along the helix in terms of the amount of whorls in the shell:

$$W = L + P$$

In order to translate this value in a distance from the apex (relative to shell height) and distance along the helix (in mm relative to the length in helicoidal direction), a 0.01 mm precision digital caliper was used to measure the height of each whorl at the position of the reference line (H_{whorl}) and the diameter of the whorl perpendicular to the plane that contains the reference line and the columella (D_{whorl} ; see **Fig S2**). The position of every sample relative to shell height could then be calculated by adding up the heights of all whorls preceding the whorl that contains the sample together with the height of the whorl that contains the sample multiplied with the position of the sample relative to the reference line:

$$h = \sum_{i=0}^{i=L} H_{whorl}(i) + H_{whorl}(L) * P$$

The position of every sample measured in distance along the length of the shell in helicoidal direction is determined by adding up the circumferences of all whorls preceding the whorl that contains the sample

together with the circumference of the whorl that contains the sample multiplied with the position of the sample relative to the reference line. In this formula, the length along the shell helix of a whorl level is approximated by the diameter of a circle with a diameter equal to that of the whorl.

$$d = \pi * \sum_{i=0}^{i=L} D_{whorl}(i) + \pi * D_{whorl}(L) * P$$

Volume of the amount of shell material at the moment when the aragonite of the sample in question was deposited (V_{cone}) was calculated by approximating the shape of the shell by a cone with a height equal to the position of the sample relative to shell height (h) and a base surface area calculated from the diameter of the whorl in which the sample is located:

$$V_{cone} = \frac{h}{3} \pi * \left(\frac{D_{whorl}(L)}{2}\right)^2$$

The volume of aragonite (V_a) is calculated by multiplying the volume of the cone by the fraction of the cross sectional area of the shell that contains aragonite (f ; total area – area of the whorls in cross section):

$$V_a = V_{cone} * f$$

Relative timing of sample positions along the helix on the outside of the shell (IRMS transects on **C2**, **E2** and **E3**) with sample positions on the shell interior (IRMS transects in **C2** and **E1** and XRF transects on all shells) was established using information about the timing of the growth of the shells in cross section (**Fig S1**). This allowed all proxy records to be plotted relative to the same axis.

Fig S2: Image of the outside of shell **C2** after sampling for stable isotope analyses. Indicated on the shell are the parameters named above and used to determine the distance of the sample from the apex along

the helix of the shell or relative to its height. Red dotted line shows the reference line used to calculate these parameters and the black line shows the direction of growth in helicoidal direction.

An age model was created linking distance along the shell (both relative to shell height and along the helix) to time of growth based on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records measured in the shells. For this age model, depth-series of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values were fed into a MATLAB routine developed by Emily Judd et al. (2018). This routine approximates the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record by combining a sinusoidal growth rate curve and sinusoidal temperature curve from which a $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ curve is calculated. Difference between modelled and measured $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values is minimized with an optimization algorithm for each year of growth recorded in the data. The modelled data is then used to infer changes in growth rate in the shells, which are translated to rates of increase in shell volume, height and length along helix with time using the record of these parameters calculated according to the formulae above.